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1. Rashidova Manzura Bakhtiyorovna THE INFLUENCE OF CONFUCIAN TRADITIONS ON THE KOREAN LANGUAGE.....	5
2. Alisher Rustamov Abduhakimovich A SYSTEM OF EXERCISES AND TASKS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF WRITTEN SPEECH SKILLS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS.....	10
3. Ziyayeva Kamola Ziyaiddinovna THE LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL DIMENSIONS OF HUMOUR: A STUDY OF SPEECH GENRES AND THEIR ROLE IN COMMUNICATIN.....	15
4. Davlatova Xulkaroy Uktamovna, Botiova Valida Shuhrat qizi SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF SPEECH COMMUNICATION AND INTERNET COMMUNICATION.....	19
5. Jo‘raqulova Mushtariy O‘ZBEK TILI PARALLEL KORPUSINING LINGVISTIK TA‘MINOTI.....	24
6. Pardayeva Iroda Mamayunusovna ALISHER NAVOIY IJODIDA AMIR TEMUR VA TEMURIYLAR TASVIRI.....	29
7. Aliyeva Zebo Akram qizi MIRATIVLIK KATEGORIYASI GRAMMATIK KO‘RSATKICH SIFATIDA.....	35
8. Mirzayev Shukurullo Abduqodir o‘g‘li TOPIK II 53- YOZISH SAVOL TURLARI VA YOZISH USULLARI.....	41
9. Bayonkhanova Iroda Furkatovna KOREYS TILINI O‘RGANISHDA MAQOLLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AFZALLIKLARI.....	47
10. Hasanov Suhrob Shavkat ugli SYMBOLS AND ALLEGORIES IN THE PROSE OF ISAJON SULTAN.....	53
11. Улаш Нематович Бобоев МОДЕЛЬ СТРАТЕГИЙ ПЕРЕВОДА НА РУССКИЙ ЯЗЫК ШОК-ТЕЙМЕНТА В СМИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И ФРАНЦИИ.....	60
12. Sadriddinzoda Safiya Shaxobiddinovna AMPHIBOLOGY IN ENGLISH RELIGIOUS LEXICOLOGY.....	65
13. Eshimova Sharofat Kenjaboyevna SINESTEZIYA - METAFORANING BIR TURI SIFATIDA.....	70
14. Umirzoqova Oynisa THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE TEMPORAL CATEGORY IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES.....	76
15. Alibekova Dilrabo Abdiraimovna COHISION OF NATURALISM, OPTIMISM AND REALISIM IN THE WORKS OF HECTOR MALOT AND THEODOR DREISER.....	83
16. Gulirukhsor Ruzikulova Gofur kizi A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF FACE-RELATED IDIOMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK.....	88
17. Xalimova Firuza Rustamovna MATN DOIRASIDA BADIY KONSEPTNING SHAKLLANISHI.....	96
18. Xamidova Dilorom Olimjonovna LUQMON BO‘RIXONNING “JAZIRAMADAGI ODAMLAR” ROMANIDA BADIY TILNING IFODALANISHI.....	102

19. Xaydarova Nigora Tuxtasunovna AYOL VA ERKAKLARNING MULOQOT USULLARI.....	107
20. Shamshoda Rustamova O‘SMIR BOLALAR NUTQIDAGI INNOVATSIYALAR VA ULARNING IFODALANISHI.....	112
21. Karshieva Shokhista Kholikul kizi SYNTAX AND SEMANTICS OF ERGATIVE CONSTRUCTIONS.....	119
22. Musayeva Shaxlo Kudratovna QISSALARDA IKKINCHI JAHON URUSHI DAVRI VOQEALARI TASVIRINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI. (Nosir Fozilov asarlari misolida).....	125
23. N.J.Sulaymanova IJOBIY BAHO PRAGMATIK MAZMUNINI IFODALOVCHI NUTQIY AKTLAR.....	131
24. Azimbayeva Nargiza Tuxtamuradovna O‘ZBEK VA FORS TILLARIDA XULQ-ATVORNI IFODALOVCHI LEKSIK KONSTRUKSIYALAR TASNIFI.....	135
25. Yuldasheva Dilnoza Bekmuradovna THE ROLE OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGY IN CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION.....	139
26. Gulruxsor Xoliyorova TERMINOLOGIK TEZAVRUSLARNING LINGVISTIK XOSLANISHI.....	143
27. Alisher Rustamov Abduhakimovich THE HISTORY OF TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH WRITING SKILLS IN UZBEKISTAN (POST-SOVIET STATE). PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTIC APPROACH.....	149
28. Kubaeva Nafisa Alisher qizi UNLOCKING THE POWER OF IDIOMS: HOW FIGURATIVE LANGUAGE ENRICHES COMMUNICATION.....	154
29. Dilafro‘z Amonova KOREYS ADABIYOTI TARIXIDA AYOLLAR IJODIYOTI.....	158
30. Obruyeva Gulchexra Xamrokulovna ATOQLI OTLARNING FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLAR TARKIBIDA APELLATIVIZATSIYAGA UCHRASHI...	164
31. Esanova Maftuna Bahodirovna YUNON-LOTIN TIBBIYOT ATAMALARINING TARIXI VA ULARNING ZAMONAVIY TIBBIYOTDAGI O‘RNI.....	168
32. Azimova Yulduz Baxtiyor qizi AVTOBIOGRAFIK DISKURSNING UMUMIY TAVSIFI.....	173
33. Maxmudova Dilshoda Kurbonbayevna KOMPOZITSION TASHKILLANISH VA PEYZAJ MODIFIKATSIYASI.....	177

Ziyayeva Kamola Ziyaiddinovna
Tashkent State university of Economics
Andijan Faculty Teacher
ziyayevakamola86@gmail.com

THE LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL DIMENSIONS OF HUMOUR: A STUDY OF SPEECH GENRES AND THEIR ROLE IN COMMUNICATIN

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ABSTRACT

Humor, a multifaceted phenomenon, plays a crucial role in human communication, serving both as a form of entertainment and a strategic tool to influence social interactions. This article explores humor as a speech genre, examining its various forms in art, communication, and culture. The study investigates humor from both linguistic and cultural perspectives, focusing on its role in different social contexts, from casual jokes to political satire. The paper highlights the challenges of translating humor, particularly due to language-specific features such as pronunciation, homonymy, and wordplay, which may not translate across cultures. Through examples of various types of linguistic humor, the article emphasizes the importance of understanding the relationship between language, culture, and humor in both its creation and reception. Ultimately, the study underscores the complexity of humor as a linguistic and cultural tool, suggesting that its effectiveness is deeply rooted in the historical, social, and cognitive contexts of the speaker and listener.

Key words: Humor, Speech genre, Linguistic humor, Cultural humor, Language and culture, Social influence, Translation of humor, Wordplay, Homonymy, Pronunciation jokes, Linguistic features, Communication strategies, Political satire, Interpersonal communication, National humor, Cognitive humor.

Зияева Камола Зияиддиновна
Ташкентский государственный университет экономики
Андижанский факультет Учительница
ziyayevakamola86@gmail.com

АННОТАЦИЯ

Юмор, многогранное явление, играет важную роль в человеческой коммуникации, служа как формой развлечения, так и стратегическим инструментом для влияния на социальные взаимодействия. В статье рассматривается юмор как речевой жанр, исследуются его различные формы в искусстве, общении и культуре. Исследование анализирует юмор с лингвистической и культурной точек зрения, акцентируя внимание на его роли в различных социальных контекстах, от повседневных шуток до политической сатиры. В работе подчеркиваются трудности перевода юмора, особенно из-за специфических особенностей языка, таких как произношение, омонимия и игра слов, которые могут не передаваться в других культурах. На примере различных типов лингвистического юмора статья акцентирует

внимание на важности понимания взаимосвязи языка, культуры и юмора в процессе его создания и восприятия. В заключение подчеркивается сложность юмора как лингвистического и культурного инструмента, эффективность которого глубоко зависит от исторических, социальных и когнитивных контекстов говорящего и слушающего.

Ключевые слова: Юмор, Речевой жанр, Лингвистический юмор, Культурный юмор, Язык и культура, Социальное влияние, Перевод юмора, Игра слов, Омонимия, Ожоговые шутки, Лингвистические особенности, Коммуникационные стратегии, Политическая сатира, Межличностная коммуникация, Национальный юмор, Когнитивный юмор.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ko‘p qirrali hodisa bo‘lgan hazil, insonlar o‘rtasidagi muloqotda muhim o‘rin tutadi, u ham o‘yin-kulgi shakli, ham ijtimoiy o‘zaro munosabatlarga ta’sir etuvchi strategik vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi. Maqolada hazil nutqiy janr sifatida ko‘rib chiqiladi va uning san‘at, muloqot va madaniyatdagi turli shakllari o‘rganiladi. Tadqiqot hazilni lingvistik va madaniy nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilib, uning turli ijtimoiy kontekstlarda, kundalik hazillardan tortib siyosiy satiragacha bo‘lgan roliga e’tibor qaratadi. Maqolada hazilni tarjima qilishdagi qiyinchiliklar, xususan, talaffuz, omonimiya va boshqa madaniyatlarga to‘liq tarjima qilinmasligi mumkin bo‘lgan so‘z o‘yini kabi o‘ziga xos til xususiyatlari tufayli ta’kidlangan. Shunindek, lingvistik hazilning har xil turlari misolida til, madaniyat va hazil o‘rtasidagi munosabatni tushunish, uni yaratish va idrok etish jarayonlari muhim ekanligi haqida so‘z yuritilgan. Xulosada hazilning lingvistik va madaniy vosita sifatida murakkabligi, uning samaradorligi so‘zlovchi va tinglovchining tarixiy, ijtimoiy va kognitiv kontekstlariga uzviy bog‘liqligi ko‘rsatilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Hazil, Nutq janri, Lingvistik yumor, Madaniy hazil, Til va madaniyat, Ijtimoiy ta’sir, Hazil tarjimasi, So‘z o‘yini, Omonimiya, Yondirish hazillari, Til xususiyatlari, Muloqot strategiyalari, Siyosiy satira, Shaxslararo muloqot, Milliy yumor, Kognitiv hazil.

INTRODUCTION

Humor is a multifaceted phenomenon, in a broad sense it is considered as a disinterested approach to a certain reality of life, mixed with laughter, and in a narrow sense it is understood as funny situations and jokes that arise as a result of a person expressing his personality in various unusual or figurative ways. The first category includes various works of art, creative works, and the second includes various jokes.

Humor is a multifaceted reality of culture. The focus of the research work is on “humor” as a speech genre. Therefore, we pay special attention to the phenomenon of “humor”.

“Humor” is an integral part of our everyday life, and people use it for different purposes in their communication with each other. Someone just for fun, while someone else uses it to achieve the goal they set during conversations. For a number of reasons, it is difficult to give a clear description of the speech genre “humor”. That is why it can be considered from the point of view of various areas of linguistics, including linguistic and cultural. We find different descriptions of humor in different sources.

1. The ability to understand, see and show laughter, a humorous attitude towards something, the presence of a sense of humor. The presence of precedent names for each nation. For example, in the Uzbek nation, the hero Nasriddin Efendi can be cited, and in the English nation, Mr. Bean.

2. In art, a funny depiction of something. Caricatures serve as an example of a humorous depiction of real reality from the artist's perspective.

3. Funny and satirical speech. Light humor, rude or inappropriate humor. These can include interpersonal communication, round tables, correspondence on social networks. Sometimes there are situations when various jokes can be used even during conflicts. While jokes like this may be funny, they are actually used in a negative sense, to make fun of someone and gain an advantage in an argument.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

Alison Ross shares several ideas about humor: “the process of making someone laugh or smile”, “humor is a common phenomenon in society and a very important part of human influence”, “humor has a powerful influence, it is used in political satire as a way to establish friendships and maintain other relationships through humor”. Therefore, humor has a social essence. Humor cannot arise or exist outside of human society. It arises within the people, among the masses, is aimed at fulfilling a specific goal, is aimed at fulfilling a specific task. True humor serves a person, for society. Therefore, it is impossible to imagine it without its social essence, without its role in the people.

D. Long and A. Gresser define humor as “an individual cognitive phenomenon of cultural form, dependent on cultural aspects, since social factors are the main mechanisms in the occurrence of humor. Humor is interpreted as various manifestations of the inconsistencies of life and artistic expressiveness. Humor is not an emotion, but a philosophy of life. It is one of the most important aspects of humanity and an integral component of any language.” Focusing on the definitions of humor given by these scientists, we believe that it would be appropriate to pay attention to the figurative means of expression of the original language and the national culture of the speakers when translating anecdotal texts. Below, the types of the “humor” speech genre and their explanations in various dictionaries and sources will be studied.

“Comedy” is a stage work in which events, actions and conflicts are depicted on the basis of laughter. This text is “a type of dramatic work that depicts funny events in life, mocks social or family conflicts, and ridiculous, comical traits in people’s characters.” “Comedy is a type of event designed to make people laugh,” and “is also interpreted as a work, film, or show that usually ends happily, intended for laughter, and also means the funny appearance of something.”

DISCUSSION/RESULTS

Linguistic humor is only known to those with high knowledge who can effectively use language in sociolinguistic conditions and enjoy communicating. It is interpreted differently in linguistics and rhetoric. In linguistics, humor is used to create a funny situation using various linguistic resources. In rhetoric, it is considered a communicative strategy that causes laughter using verbal and nonverbal sources of communication. Scientists who have conducted research on the text and language of humor have developed its analytical paradigm and definition. In order to adequately answer questions in the process of studying linguistic humor, linguists have classified the internal and external aspects of verbal humor.

- General rules of jokes
- Mechanism of jokes
- Features that ensure the effectiveness of jokes
- Humorous relations between the speaker and the listener
- Personality, mentality, origin of the speaker and the listener, etc.

National humor is considered a linguistic and cultural phenomenon, which embodies historical realities, traditions, values, national character, etc. The extralinguistic coloring in it determines the boundaries for national humor. This is because actions that are a source of laughter for one nation may be incomprehensible and unusual for another nation. To understand it, the environment related to the nation and the situation in which the joke occurred must be studied.

When classifying linguistic jokes, the following speech-specific features are taken into account, namely pronunciation (speech distortion and dialect), onomatopoeia (the use of different sounds in language), homonymy, etc.

Pronunciation jokes:

The internet has finally determined the true pronunciation of “GIF”

It is “g” in garage.

In this example, the comic situation arises from the different pronunciation of one letter within the same linguistic unit. When translating some jokes, their comical nature disappears. The main reason for this is that there are letters in the English language that have two or more pronunciations, as well as the property of not being pronounced. This joke and idea are often one of the most popular memes on the Internet and social networks. Based on the ongoing discussions and debates about the correct pronunciation of “GIF”, many funny and changing opinions arise. It is difficult to find the exact source

of the joke, because these types of memes and funny quotes often appear on various sites, especially Reddit, Twitter, or meme platforms.

Homonymy, that is, jokes that contain homophones and homographs:

“Waiter”

“Yes, sir”

“What’s this?”

“It’s bean soup, sir.”

“Never mind what it has been. I want to know what it is now.”

The above joke uses the homonyms "bean" and "been" to create a comic effect. A person who does not know English will not understand these jokes. If such jokes are found in movies, there is absolutely no way to translate them. Even if they are translated, the humor will not be transferred to the translation. Because, as we mentioned earlier, the word "bean" as a noun means "bean", and the linguistic unit "been" is a form of the verb "to be", which is in the third column of irregular verbs in the sentence structure used for the present perfect tense, which is characteristic of English grammar.

Jokes made using synonyms:

“What did you call a pastry that is yummy, tasty and delicious?

A synonym roll.”

Jokes based on wordplay:

Passenger: Guard! How long will the next train be?

Guard: About six carriages, sir.

In fact, this joke is impossible to translate. The reason is that the text has a feature that is unique to the English language. In the joke, the interrogative phrase “how long?” consisting of two words is used in two different meanings, that is, the first is used to ask about the length of time, and the second is used to ask about the length of time. A situation of humor arises between the interlocutors due to the lack of understanding of the exact meaning of the question.

There are many linguistic factors for creating a humorous phenomenon, but each author creates it using methods that are convenient and familiar to him. Currently, there is no system that covers all the linguistic factors that provide a comic effect.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in linguistics, the use of various features of linguistic units in humorous texts has been consistently studied for many years. They have been approached mainly from a historical-comparative and system-structural perspective. Above, we have given examples based on the research and opinions of scholars in linguistics as proof of our words and explained them. As we have seen, texts with a humorous content require a wider range of research.

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